

Net worth and Mental Health Problems

Jaewon Lee^{1*} and Jennifer Allen²

¹Department of Social Welfare, Inha University, South Korea

²School of Social Work, Michigan State University, USA

Assets and debts and other accumulated wealth should be considered to understand one's mental health because they influence quality of life over time. Researchers acknowledge limitations of previous studies regarding mental health, which did not consider net worth [1]. Previous studies have mainly addressed Socioeconomic Status (SES) as an indicator influencing mental health [2,3], rather than considering net worth. As a result, the importance of net worth (Wealth and debt) has been growing, and these factors should be included to deeply understand mental health [1].

As the amount of debt that people hold has steadily increased [4], those with a lot of debt might experience more distress and uncertainty for their future, which then leads to more stress, anger, and irritability [1]. In particular, given that stressors from debt result in cumulative disadvantage [5], being in debt limits one's ability to deal with poor mental health [1]. They may not be able to maintain their social networks, which is detrimental as social support is important for mental health [6]. Additionally, as young adults (Those in their 20s and 30s) are more likely to be in debt than older adults [7], young adults are therefore particularly at risk for mental health problems.

Drentea and Reynolds [1] illustrated how individuals in debt were likely to have poor psychological health. Being in debt has ties to depression and is negatively associated with mental health [8] and makes collecting retirement income more difficult [9]. As a result, individuals over age 65 are left with insufficient funds and have trouble accessing essential resources to maintain their quality of life [8]. On the other hand, assets help an individual attain economic security as well as develop a positive attitude toward their daily life [10]. Individuals who feel that they have sufficient economic resources tend to have better mental health. In other words, asset ownership may be beneficial to reduce mental health problems [11]. For instance, American workers who were not wealthy before the Great Recession of 2008 were more likely suffer from depressive symptoms in comparison with those who were wealthy [12]. As such, debts and assets play a significant role in changes to one's mental health.

The effects of assets on mental health can also be expanded to the intergenerational relationship between parental assets and children's mental health. Ssewamala and colleagues [11] found that household assets buffer against children's mental health problems. Since asset ownership provides a sense of comfort and encouragement that individuals can accomplish their goals, children with sufficient family economic resources feel that they have fewer barriers against them attaining a good education, for example, leading them to have fewer mental health problems [11]. Along with this, other studies support the relationship between parental assets and better psychological well-being among their children [13]. Therefore, household wealth buffers against poor mental health not only for adults, but also for children.

*Corresponding author

Jaewon Lee, Department of Social Welfare,
Inha University, 100 Inha-ro, Michuhol-gu,
Incheon 22212, South Korea

Tel: +82-32-860-9324

E-mail: j343@inha.ac.kr

DOI: 10.37871/jbres1195

Submitted: 17 February 2021

Accepted: 01 March 2021

Published: 02 March 2021

Copyright: © 2021 Lee J, et al. Distributed under
Creative Commons CC-BY 4.0

OPEN ACCESS

Subject: Medicine Group

Topic & Subtopic(s): Mental Health; Anxiety;
Depression

VOLUME: 2 ISSUE: 3

Moreover, Zurlo and colleagues [8] examined debts in a sample of older adults with an average age of 68 years, while Meltzer and colleagues [14] looked at a broader age range of adults (16 to 64 years), but all respondents were living in England. Even though these studies indicated that debts played a role as a buffer against poor mental health, their analyses were based on a cross-sectional approach and the findings were not focused on children, young adults, and middle adults. In addition, they also only addressed debts and did not consider assets [8,14]. As such, most previous studies were conducted based up a cross-sectional approach and did not examine how one's accumulated net worth influences mental health over the life course. Therefore, we suggest that future studies account for how individual and household net worth, including both assets and debts, affect one's mental health in diverse populations and generations.

References

1. Drentea P, Reynolds JR. Neither a borrower nor a lender be: the relative importance of debt and SES for mental health among older adults. *J Aging Health*. 2012 Jun;24(4):673-95. doi: 10.1177/0898264311431304. Epub 2012 Feb 13. PMID: 22330730.
2. Braveman PA, Cubbin C, Egerter S, Chideya S, Marchi KS, Metzler M, Posner S. Socioeconomic status in health research: one size does not fit all. *JAMA*. 2005 Dec 14;294(22):2879-88. doi: 10.1001/jama.294.22.2879. PMID: 16352796.
3. Laaksonen M, Rahkonen O, Martikainen P, Lahelma E. Socioeconomic position and self-rated health: the contribution of childhood socioeconomic circumstances, adult socioeconomic status, and material resources. *Am J Public Health*. 2005 Aug;95(8):1403-9. doi: 10.2105/AJPH.2004.047969. Epub 2005 Jul 7. PMID: 16006419; PMCID: PMC1449373.
4. Garcia JA. Borrowing to make ends meet: The rapid growth of credit card debt in America. New York, NY: Dēmos Publication Series. 2007:p. 1-32.
5. Ferraro KF, Shippee TP. Aging and cumulative inequality: how does inequality get under the skin? *Gerontologist*. 2009 Jun;49(3):333-43. doi: 10.1093/geront/gnp034. Epub 2009 Apr 17. PMID: 19377044; PMCID: PMC2721665.
6. Cockerham WC. Health lifestyle theory and the convergence of agency and structure. *J Health Soc Behav*. 2005 Mar;46(1):51-67. doi: 10.1177/002214650504600105. PMID: 15869120.
7. McCloud L, Dwyer R. The fragile American: Hardship and financial troubles in the 21st century. *Sociological Quarterly*. 2011 Jan 6;52(1):13-25. doi: 10.1111/j.1533-8525.2010.01197.x
8. Zurlo KA, Yoon W, Kim H. Unsecured consumer debt and mental health outcomes in middle-aged and older Americans. *J Gerontol B Psychol Sci Soc Sci*. 2014 May;69(3):461-9. doi: 10.1093/geronb/gbu020. Epub 2014 Mar 17. PMID: 24637231.
9. Loonin D, Renuart E. The life and debt cycle: The growing debt burdens of older consumers and related policy recommendations. *Harvard Journal on Legislation*. 2007 Dec;44(1):167-203.
10. Zhan M. Economic mobility of single mothers: The role of assets and human capital development. *Journal of Sociology and Social Welfare*. 2006;33(4):127-150.
11. Ssewamala FM, Han CK, Neilands TB. Asset ownership and health and mental health functioning among AIDS-orphaned adolescents: findings from a randomized clinical trial in rural Uganda. *Soc Sci Med*. 2009 Jul;69(2):191-8. doi: 10.1016/j.socscimed.2009.05.019. Epub 2009 Jun 10. PMID: 19520472; PMCID: PMC2819297.
12. Riumallo-Herl C, Basu S, Stuckler D, Courtin E, Avendano M. Job loss, wealth and depression during the Great Recession in the USA and Europe. *Int J Epidemiol*. 2014 Oct;43(5):1508-17. doi: 10.1093/ije/dyu048. Epub 2014 Jun 18. PMID: 24942142; PMCID: PMC4190512.
13. Sherraden, M. Stakeholding: Notes on a theory of welfare based on assets. *Social Service Review*. 1990 Dec;64(4):580-601. doi: 10.1086/603797.
14. Meltzer H, Bebbington P, Brugha T, Jenkins R, McManus S, Stansfeld S. Job insecurity, socio-economic circumstances and depression. *Psychol Med*. 2010 Aug;40(8):1401-7. doi: 10.1017/S0033291709991802. Epub 2009 Nov 11. PMID: 19903366.

How to cite this article: Lee J, Allen J. Net worth and Mental Health Problems. *J Biomed Res Environ Sci*. 2021 Mar 02; 2(3): 095-096. doi: 10.37871/jbres1195, Article ID: JBRES1195